

HORIZONTAL CYLINDER-IN-CYLINDER BUCKLING UNDER COMPRESSION AND TORSION: REVIEW AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY: Available analytical results and experiments on the structural behavior of constrained horizontal cylinders subjected to axial compression, torsion, and gravitational loads are reviewed. Such configurations are of interest to the oil-drilling field and provide static design expressions for steel tubulars. Due to outer cylinder constraint and gravitational loads, analysis has shown that long tubes initiate buckling at loads significantly higher than classical Euler buckling loads. For these constrained long tubes, buckling initiates in a sinusoidal mode that snakes along the lower surface of the constraining cylinder. Classic analytical expressions hold that as the axial load increases, the tube achieves an overall helically buckled state in which the buckled cylinder forms a helix spiraling around the inner surface of the constraining cylinder. Torsion is shown to have little effect on either buckling load but controls the sense/direction of the helical buckling. Little experimental data exists on constrained tube buckling, and it is unclear how the initiating sinusoidal mode transitions to the helical mode. The behavior of short tubes, where boundary conditions at the tube ends are important, is not well understood; analytic expressions that define short vs. long cylinders for this problem are introduced. Implications of the buckling progression for composite tube applications are described including the finding that composites perform poorly relative to steel on the metric of buckling due to lower density and axial stiffness. Based on this review and findings for composite tubes, recommendations are made for further work.

KEYWORDS: helical buckling, sinusoidal buckling, tube, cylinder, oil drilling, compression, torsion

I. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

This study of the structural buckling behavior of cylinders is motivated by recent interest in the use of laminated composite tubes for oil and gas drill pipe. Current oil and gas drill pipe is made from isotropic steel tubes. The switch to composite tubes is motivated by the higher specific stiffness and strength of advanced composite materials as compared to steel. The anisotropy of the composite tubes also lends itself to the possibility of custom-tuning the tubulars (via laminate design) in such a way as to optimize the structural behavior (*e.g.* being able to change the axial and bending stiffnesses independently). The weight benefits of these composite drill pipes are particularly attractive for use in offshore drilling platforms. While there are currently higher up-front costs to employ these composite tubes, these costs may be tempered by improved fatigue behavior over the steel tubes.

In this paper a review of available analyses and experiments on cylinder-in-cylinder buckling under axial compressive and torsional loads is presented. Analyses and experiments which are available are fragmented and confusing, particularly with respect to the progression and transition between numerous buckling modes. Understanding the structural behavior of drill pipe is critical in predicting and avoiding a lock-up condition, in which the drill pipe is unable to progress due to frictional interactions with the constraining tube or hole.

The situation to be analyzed is shown in Figure 1. The inner cylinder corresponds to the drill pipe. In this article, the terms “tube”, “pipe”, and “cylinder” are used interchangeably. The constraining outer cylinder corresponds either to a constraining pipe lining the wall of the hole being drilled, or to the wall of the hole itself (some drilling is performed open-hole, without any outer constraining pipe). Δr is the radial clearance between the two cylinders, and will be seen to be a critical parameter in this problem. The inner cylinder of length L is subjected to an applied axial compressive load P and a torsional load T . The cylinders are assumed to be horizontal, such that gravity acts as a distributed transverse load. The inner cylinder is assumed to be supported at its ends such that it is centered radially in the constraining outer cylinder. The outer pipe is assumed to be a rigid constraint on the displacement of the inner cylinder where the two are in contact.

Figure 1

The situation described above is an idealization. Oil wells can be very long, with some sections vertical, some inclined, some horizontal, with lengths sometimes reaching to beyond ten kilometers. Many other factors influence drill pipe structural instabilities, such as frictional effects, dynamics, bit chatter, and internal pressure from drilling fluid being pumped through the drill pipe. These factors are ignored in the present study. Friction in particular plays a critical role in drilling, as it can lead to lock-up and influence the onset and modes of buckling. As prediction and avoidance of lock-up is one of the key goals of studying these structural instabilities, researchers have attempted to incorporate friction into the structural instability analysis [1-6]. Finally, it should be noted that material/sub-structural failure modes (*e.g.* composite ply microbuckling) must be overlaid with the structural understanding for overall failure prediction and design.

Here we aim to provide a summary of analyses and experiments relevant to the idealized problem described above. In laying out the analyses, we note a qualitative difference between the structural behavior of “long” and “short” tubes. Long tubes are analytically defined and their behavior described in Section II. Section II is the focus of the review of past work on isotropic tubes – orthotropic or CLPT analyses are provided where available. Particular attention is paid to experimental evidence where it is available. Implications of these results for the use of composite tubes in drilling applications are examined in Section III.

For the purposes of this review, the following values for parameters that factor into the structural behavior of these cylinders were chosen based on steel drilling tubulars:

- Axial compressive load $P = 100,000 \text{ N}$ (22,480 lb)
- Torsional load $T = 20,000 \text{ N-m}$ (14,750 ft-lb)
- Inner cylinder dimensions: OD = 14.0 cm (5.5in), ID = 11.6 cm (4.6in)
- Outer cylinder dimensions: ID = 22.2 cm (8.5in)
- Inner cylinder length $L = 2000 \text{ m}$ (6561 ft)
- Radial clearance between inner and outer cylinders $\Delta r = 4.1 \text{ cm}$
- Young’s modulus $E(\text{steel}) = 207 \text{ GPa}$ (~30 Msi)
- Cross-sectional moment of inertia $I = 9.97\text{E-}6 \text{ m}^4$
- Cross-sectional area $A = 0.00483 \text{ m}^2$
- Density ρ (steel) = 7900 kg/m^3
- Weight per unit length of pipe w (steel) = 374 N/m (25.6 lb/ft)
- Nominal average axial stress: $\sigma = -21 \text{ MPa}$
- Nominal average shear stress: $\tau = 65 \text{ MPa}$

For comparison, composite tubulars typical values are:

- E (composite) = 35 GPa (5 Msi)
- ρ (composite) = 1600 kg/m^3
- w (composite) = 76 N/m (5.2 lb/ft)

II. STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR OF “LONG” HORIZONTAL PIPES

A “long” pipe is sufficiently long such that the majority of the inner pipe lays on the bottom of the constraining outer pipe. Enough of the inner pipe is in contact with the constraining pipe that the boundary conditions at the pipe ends do not affect the buckling behavior – “long” is quantified in a later section using parameters obtained from the buckling analysis.

An unconstrained cylinder subjected to torsion and axial compression will undergo classical Euler buckling [7]. This coupling of torsion and axial load is well understood. An Euler surface can be constructed to visualize this compression-torsion interaction. As will be seen later, the classical Euler buckling load is significantly lower than the minimum buckling load for the constrained tube case.

The buckling progression of long pipes is summarized in Table 1. First, the pipe bends under its own weight, and this bending is well understood in the context of Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. Upon bending under its own weight, the majority of pipe lays on the bottom of the outer pipe. The pipe lying on the bottom becomes the prebuckling state for the first (sinusoidal) buckle. Buckling initiates in the pipe lying on the bottom of the outer cylinder in a sinusoidal mode that follows the walls of the constraining cylinder (the post-buckled pipe ‘snakes’ along the bottom of the constraining pipe). Last, the buckling progresses to a helical mode in which the inner pipe forms a helix spiraling around the inner wall of the outer cylinder. These buckling modes are described in detail in the following sub-

sections. Section 2.3 includes a discussion of the transition from the sinusoidal to helical mode.

Mode Name	Load	Mode Visualization
1. Pipe Bends Under Own Weight	$\delta \propto wL^4/EI$	 Side View ↓ gravity
2. Constrained Euler Sinusoid (n=2)	$P_{cr}^s = 2\sqrt{EI w/\Delta r}$	 Top View Side View
3. Constrained Euler Helical (m=1)	$P_{cr}^h = 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{EI w/\Delta r}$	 Top View Side View

Table 1: Long tube buckling progression.

2.1 Constrained Euler Sinusoidal Buckling

The first buckling mode that the long pipe will undergo is what will be referred to here as constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling [3, 4, 8-13]. In this mode, the pipe snakes along the bottom surface of the outer pipe, as shown in Table 1. The inner pipe remains in contact with the constraining pipe along the entire length of the pipes. The prebuckling mode is of the inner pipe lying on the bottom of the constraining pipe. Paslay and Bogoy derived this solution originally using an energy method applied to a general displacement field [8]. The solution is a small-amplitude, small-angle approximation, so it is useful to predict the first buckle, but not the subsequent behavior of the cylinder.

The displacement field of the inner pipe centerline for this mode (see illustration in Figure 2) is described by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_3 &= \Delta r \sin \beta \\
 u_2 &= \Delta r(1 - \cos \beta) \\
 \beta &= \beta_0 \sin\left(\frac{n\pi}{L}x\right) \\
 p &= \frac{2L}{n}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The angle β is shown in Figure 2. u_2 and u_3 are the displacements of the inner pipe centerline in the y and z direction, respectively (shown in Figure 2). p is the wavelength of the sinusoidal buckle, and n the number of half-wavelengths of the sinusoidal buckle. The critical buckling load for this mode with the cylinder subject only to compression and gravity (neglecting torsion) is [8]:

$$P_{cr}^s = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \left(n^2 + \frac{L^4 \rho A g}{n^2 \pi^4 EI \Delta r} \right) \tag{2}$$

The first term in (2) is the classical Euler buckling load. The second term is proportional to the weight per unit length of the pipe, and is of the same form as the buckling load of a beam

on an elastic foundation. The equivalent elastic foundation constant is $\frac{\rho Ag}{\Delta r}$. The equivalence with a beam on an elastic foundation stems from the expression for the vertical displacement of the mode, u_2 in (1). For small displacements, this vertical displacement is proportional to β^2 . This results in a change in gravitational potential energy also proportional to β^2 , akin to the potential energy of a spring, which is proportional to displacement squared.

Figure 2: Displacement field of constrained Euler sinusoidal buckle

The buckling load for a constrained Euler sinusoidal buckle as a function of pipe length and half wavelength n for the common pipe parameters given in Section 1 is shown in Figure 3. As the pipe length increases, the minima become shallower, resulting in a buckling load that is nearly independent of length. This length-independent buckling load is:

$$P_{cr}^s = 2 \left(\frac{EI\rho Ag}{\Delta r} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

The buckling wavelength is a function of the tube bending stiffness, the weight per unit length of the inner tube, and the level of constraint of the outer tube (Δr):

$$n = \frac{L}{\pi} \left(\frac{\rho Ag}{EI\Delta r} \right)^{1/4} \quad (4)$$

For the common pipe parameters given in Section 1, this corresponds to $n = 165$. This is in contrast with classical unconstrained Euler buckling, where the first buckle is always a half sinusoid (equivalent to $n = 1$). The normal force per unit length for a tube undergoing sinusoidal buckling has been presented in several studies [3, 13]:

$$W_n = \frac{16\pi^4 EI\Delta r \beta_0^2}{p^4} \left(-\beta_0^2 \cos^4 \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x \right) + 3 \sin^2 \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x \right) - 4 \cos^2 \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x \right) \right) + \frac{4\pi^2 \Delta r \beta_0^2 P}{p^2} \cos^2 \left(\frac{n\pi}{L} x \right) + w \cos \beta \quad (5)$$

Deli, Wu, and Ye [10] include torsion in deriving the buckling load for constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling. Torsion enters the equilibrium equations through the dimensionless parameter $\frac{\sqrt{2T}}{\sqrt{FEI}}$. This parameter shows the relative influence of torsion to compression. For the drilling parameters given in Section 1, this parameter has value of 0.06, so the load given in (2), which neglects torsion, is a good approximation for these drill pipe parameters.

There is limited experimental evidence of the constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling mode. Chen, Lin, Cheatham [14] do describe experiments, and give some sinusoidal buckling initiation loads for these experiments. However, these loads are nearly double the

buckling loads calculated from (2) [15]. Wu and Juvkam-Wold [4] describe experiments in which they confirm the sinusoidal buckling mode, buckling load, and wavelength predicted by (2), (3), and (4). Miska et al. [3] present experimental results in which they report a stable sinusoidal buckle at loads above that given in (3) – the initiation load for sinusoidal buckle is not reported. Kuru et al. [5] also report the appearance of sinusoidal buckles; no direct measurement of sinusoidal buckle initiation load is reported.

Figure 3: Constrained Euler sinusoidal (solid lines) and helical (dashed lines) buckling loads plotted as a function of cylinder length and wavelength for the nominal steel case.

Using (4), “long” pipe can be quantified. The pipe is required to be long enough that there will be at least 10 half-wavelengths of buckled sinusoid in the region of pipe lying along the bottom of the outer cylinder (taking into account the region at either end where the inner pipe is *not* lying on the bottom of the outer cylinder). This gives $L > 37.2 \left(\frac{EI\Delta r}{w} \right)^{1/4}$ to define a long pipe, where L is the total length of the inner pipe. For the steel pipe parameters given in Section 1, $L > 143$ meters.

2.2 Constrained Euler Helical Buckling

As the load on the inner cylinder increases, the buckling mode progresses from the constrained Euler sinusoidal buckle to an overall helical buckling mode which will be termed constrained Euler helical buckling here [4-6, 10, 12-14, 16, 17]. In this mode, the inner pipe forms a helix wrapping around the inner wall of the outer pipe. Chen et al. [14] use a straightforward energy analysis to show that the axial buckling load (again neglecting torsion) for this constrained Euler helical mode to buckle from a straight configuration (again lying at the bottom of the constraining cylinder) is:

$$P_{cr}^h = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \left(4m^2 + \frac{L^4 \rho Ag}{2m^2 \pi^4 EI \Delta r} \right) \quad (6)$$

Buckling loads for this constrained Euler helical buckle as a function of pipe length and m (the helix full wavelength) for the common drill pipe parameters given in Section I are shown in Figure 3. As is the case for the constrained Euler sinusoidal mode, as the pipe length increases, the local minima become shallower, resulting in a buckling load that is nearly independent of length. This length-independent buckling load is:

$$P_{cr}^h = 2\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{EI\rho Ag}{\Delta r} \right)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

Note that this load is $\sqrt{2}$ (~41%) higher than the length-independent constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling load given in (3). Note also that, in order for frictional interactions to raise the constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling load to that of the constrained Euler helical buckling load, the frictional interactions would need to effectively double the weight per unit length. As with the sinusoidal buckle, the buckling full wavelength is a function of the tube bending stiffness, the weight per unit length of the inner tube, and the level of constraint of the outer tube (Δr):

$$m = \frac{L}{\pi} \left(\frac{\rho Ag}{8EI\Delta r} \right)^{1/4} \quad (8)$$

For the common pipe parameters given in Section I, this corresponds to $m = 98$.

For this constrained Euler helical mode, Lubinski [16] showed that the applied compressive load and pitch of the helically postbuckled tube can be related by:

$$P^h = 8\pi^2 EI / p^2 ; P^h > P_{cr}^h \quad (9)$$

As the compressive load increases, the inner cylinder forms a helix with a smaller pitch. Mitchell [2] showed that the normal force per unit length at the constraining wall for a frictionless helically buckled pipe is:

$$W_n = \frac{\Delta r P^2}{4EI} + w \cos \beta \quad (10)$$

The second term reflects the intuitive notion of gravity's effect on the normal force (e.g., tube weight adds to the normal force when on the bottom of the constraining cylinder and subtracts when at the top). The first term shows that as the applied compressive load increases, the normal force will increase quickly. In practice this can lead to substantial frictional forces resisting axial motion and eventually to lock-up [4, 6], when frictional forces along the length of the inner pipe balance the maximum compressive load applied at the end of the inner pipe. Note that (10) ignores the role of friction, but this result does indicate how the normal force scales with the applied axial load.

Torsion enters the governing equilibrium differential equation for constrained Euler helical buckling in the same dimensionless parameter as for constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling [10]. As was shown in Section 2.2, this dimensionless parameter is small for the common drilling parameters given in Section I, so torsion has a small effect on the constrained helical buckling load. However, torsion will determine the sense of the helix.

Deli, Wu, and Ye [10] show that for a constrained cylinder subject to gravitational, torsional, and compressive loads, the helically postbuckled solution has a non-uniform helix angle – that is, the rate of change of angle in the x-direction depends upon position. The helical pitch, however, is uniform/constant, and is the same as for the weightless tube. This helical pitch with compression and torsion can be found via [10, 18]:

$$P^h = 8\pi^2 EI / p^2 - 3T\pi / p \quad (11)$$

Qiu [13] calculates the normal force per unit length at the constraining wall for a helically buckled pipe under compression and torsion:

$$W_n = \frac{\Delta r P}{128(EI)^2} \left(3T + \sqrt{9T^2 + 32EIP} \right) \left(T + \sqrt{9T^2 + 32EIP} \right) + w \cos \beta \quad (12)$$

Torsion can be shown to enter this expression in the same dimensionless parameter as previously mentioned, and thus plays a small role in this normal force. This expression simplifies to (10) when the torsional load vanishes.

Some authors have observed the constrained Euler helical buckling mode. Most of these authors studied significantly more complicated borehole geometries than that considered here. Some experimental evidence of the constrained Euler helical mode is presented in Chen, Lin, Cheatham [14]. Lubinski [9, 19] also presents some experimental results of this mode. Martinez et al. [1] performed experiments to investigate the frictional forces exerted on helically buckled tubes. Wu and Juvkam-Wold [4] experimentally investigated the development of axial load during the transition from sinusoidal to helical buckle. Several studies have also been undertaken to investigate the development of axial load of helically buckled tubes, including the influence of friction on that axial load development [3, 5]. Pastusek and Van Brackin [20] include a photo of helical wear scars on drill pipe. These sorts of scars are typically shown as evidence of helical buckling in service (although they can equally be an indication of hole spiraling, *i.e.* the inner tube is straight and the outer tube itself has helical form).

Chen, Lin, and Cheatham [14] note that substituting half of the number of half-wavelengths of sinusoidal buckle for the number of full wavelengths of helical buckles ($m = n/2$) into (6) yields:

$$P_{cr}^h = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \left(n^2 + \frac{2L^4 \rho A g}{n^2 \pi^4 E I r} \right) \quad (13)$$

The first term in (13) is the same as the first term in the constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling load given by (2), while the second term is twice as large for the constrained Euler helical mode, showing that, for buckles of the same wavelength, the second term gives rise to the difference in buckling load between these two modes.

2.3 Transition Between Constrained Euler Sinusoidal and Helical Modes

Transition from sinusoid to helix has not been analyzed in detail by many researchers [21], nor has it been well-documented experimentally. Many researchers have shown (via analysis and experiment) that constrained Euler helical buckling occurs at higher loads than the constrained Euler sinusoid mode. Helical buckling *is* seen experimentally, but the transition from a prebuckled state (particularly the constrained sinusoid mode) has not been described in detail. This transition is complicated, as the sinusoidal mode wraps around the constraining pipe in alternating senses, while the helical mode forms a helix that wraps around the constraining pipe in only one direction/sense. He and Kyllingstad [6] note that in their experiments, which involved compressive axial loads but no torsion, the helical mode actually had reversal of pitch sense, but the details of this process are not explained.

Again neglecting torsion and friction, several analytical studies have shown that the helical solution is valid for $P > \sqrt{2}P_{cr}^s$, and that the sinusoidal solution is not valid for $P > 2\sqrt{2}P_{cr}^s$ [14, 21]. When the axial load reaches $2\sqrt{2}P_{cr}^s$ (or, equivalently, twice P_{cr}^h), the buckling mode must have transitioned all the way to helical. Thus, the transition must occur in the range:

$$\sqrt{2}P_{cr}^s < P < 2\sqrt{2}P_{cr}^s \quad (\text{or, equivalently, } P_{cr}^h < P < 2P_{cr}^h) \quad (14)$$

Many researchers have attempted to analytically quantify precisely where in this range the transition occurs [3, 4, 12, 18, 21]. Wu and Juvkam-Wold [4] assume that as the tube transitions from a sinusoidal to helical mode, the buckling load increases from P_{cr}^s , with

the increase proportional to the change in length of the tube as it transitions. They assume that the *average* axial load over the transition is P_{cr}^h . Under these assumptions, for the tube to *fully* transition from sinusoidal to helical buckling, the axial load must be about 30% higher than P_{cr}^h . Some experimental evidence is provided to support these assumptions. Qiu, Miska, Volk, and Cunha [3, 12] show that the sinusoidal mode becomes unstable at an axial load also about 30% higher than P_{cr}^h . It is assumed that the tube undergoes helical buckling at loads higher than this value, and some experimental evidence that suggests that this assumption is correct is provided. Mitchell [21] solves the differential form of equilibrium equations assuming a helical buckle displacement field. This analysis predicts that the transition to helical buckling occurs at an axial load of twice P_{cr}^h . So, under different assumptions and with some experimental evidence, the long tube fully transitions from the sinusoidal buckle to helical buckle between $\sim 1.3P_{cr}^h$ and $2P_{cr}^h$.

In the preceding two sections, we treat the discrete possibilities of being in one or the other of the buckled states, ignoring the transition between the states. Past researchers have made the assumption of a smooth transition between these states. There appears to be an opportunity for an intermediate state between sinusoidal and helical buckling, or that the transition between the two is not smooth (*i.e.* the two states may be bistable over some range of axial load), as the sinusoidal mode involves the inner tube wrapping in alternating senses around the outer tube, while the helical mode involves wrapping in only one sense. Furthermore, when friction is considered, it will influence the entire buckling progression, and the inequality (14) stating the transition is likely not applicable. In the case where torsion and axial load are considered, there are orthogonal frictional components that further influence the buckling progression. This more complicated load case (axial load, torsion, gravity, and friction) is the subject of ongoing analysis.

2.4 Other Buckling Modes

In general, several buckling modes relevant for thin-walled tubes must be considered. For typical drilling geometry and loads, these thin-walled buckling modes are not seen, as their buckling loads are much higher than the loads encountered in drilling. These modes include thin-walled helical buckling under a torsional load and concertina buckling under a compressive load. Thin-walled modes are discussed in detail by Bazant and Cedolin [7].

2.5 Structural Behavior of “Short” Pipes

There are several drilling applications in which short tubes are used. In these applications, the majority of pipe does not lay along the bottom surface of the outer pipe. Clearly in this case the boundary conditions have a large effect on the buckling behavior. Common short tube applications have a tighter fit of the inner pipe in the outer pipe, which can play a role in the buckling progression, as was seen in the behavior of long pipes. The buckling progression of short pipes is not well understood, and this progression merits further study.

III. IMPLICATIONS FOR COMPOSITE TUBES

As was mentioned in section I, study of this problem is strongly motivated by an interest in switching from isotropic steel pipe to laminated composite pipe. In this section some of the implications of the long tube buckling progression analyses (sections 2.1 and 2.2) on composite pipes versus steel pipes are explored.

A typical value of the effective axial modulus of a polymer matrix carbon-fiber composite drill tube is 35 GPa, though certainly there is a strong dependence on the particular lay-up of the tube. Steel has a higher Young's modulus of 207 GPa. The other relevant difference between steel and composite tubes is the density. As drilling is performed in the presence of a drilling fluid (substantially the same drilling fluid inside and outside the drill pipe), the buoyancy of the pipe in this fluid leads to an effective density, which is the density of the pipe material minus the density of the drilling fluid. Typical values of density for steel are 7900 kg/m^3 , while for polymer matrix carbon-fiber composites, densities are normally close to 1600 kg/m^3 . Densities of drilling fluids are typically close to 1250 kg/m^3 . This makes the effective densities for steel and composite tubes 6650 kg/m^3 and 350 kg/m^3 , respectively, meaning typical composite tubes are effectively $1/20^{\text{th}}$ the density of steel tubes.

In considering a switch from steel to composite tubes, the modulus and weight are the primary governing parameters. While in other composite applications *geometry* can be modified, for drilling applications the tube geometry is often fixed (or nearly fixed). That is, the outer radius of the drill pipe is determined by the hole size desired, and the inner radius determined by issues related to the pressure drop of drilling fluid being pumped and the desired pipe strength. Thus, for the comparison here, only the change in modulus and density need be considered.

The differences in stiffness and effective density lead to significant differences in structural behavior. Long composite tubes initiate constrained Euler sinusoidal and helical buckling at lower loads than steel tubes – for typical values, composite tubes buckle at loads less than $1/10^{\text{th}}$ of those for steel tubes. Buckling is anticipated to occur at lower loads for short composite tubes also. It should be noted that friction in this comparative analysis between composite and steel may change the conclusion regarding relative performance. As friction is a first-order contributing factor to lock-up, and friction is a function of normal force between the pipes, then due to the increased buoyancy of composites as compared to steel, there may be some advantage to composite tubes that offsets the buckling load reduction due to density and stiffness considerations. This is the subject of ongoing research.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The available analyses and experiments exploring the structural progression of long pipes are documented in section II of this paper. The behavior/progression of long pipes is well understood analytically for isotropic, frictionless pipes, aside from the transition from constrained Euler sinusoidal buckling to constrained Euler helical buckling. This transition merits further experimental study. For long pipes subject to compression, torsion, gravity, *and* friction, the buckling modes are not well understood. This is the subject of current research being undertaken analytically.

This article serves to review the buckling progression of constrained long pipes in a comprehensive fashion. The progression is clear from past research, but this has been scattered over many papers. This has led to a difficulty in developing a clear picture of what this buckling progression looks like and what are the relevant parameters. Pipe designers can combine this buckling behavior with material/ply-level failure in a relatively straightforward way to ensure robust design.

The structural buckling progression of short pipes has not been the subject of analysis and is not well understood. Short pipe behavior will be necessarily dependent on boundary conditions at pipe ends. Further work in this area is needed to characterize short pipe behavior.

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